

Action of Acetic Butyric Anhydride on Acetone-Dicarboxylic Acid

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Reaction between acetic-butyric anhydride and acetonedicarboxylic acid gave as the major product 2-*n*-propyl 5-acetyl 4:6 diketo 5:6 dihydro γ pyran carboxylic acid-3. Decarboxylation of the latter followed by boiling with hydrochloric acid gave the hydrochloride of 2-*n*-propyl 6-methyl γ pyrone. The latter is not however identical with the pyrone of the same structure prepared by a different route as the two pyrones differ in their physical properties.

THE action of a symmetrical anhydride $R-CO-O-CO-R$ on acetone-dicarboxylic acid (I) results in acylation at both the methylene groups of (I) followed by cyclisation to the lactone carboxylic acid (II). Decarboxylation of the latter gives the lactone (III).^{1,2}

This paper describes the result of reaction of the unsymmetrical acetic-butyric anhydride $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO-O-CO-C}_3\text{H}_7$ on (I).

This anhydride is described by Hurd and Dull³ who prepared it from ketene and *n*-butyric acid and who mention that it has a wide boiling range 147°-160°. Autenrieth⁴ prepared it from acetic anhydride and *n*-butyric acid and gives 155°-175° as its boiling range. An attempt at narrowing the range by fractionation results in its breakdown to acetic and butyric anhydrides.

When (I) was treated with this anhydride under conditions as in the case of symmetrical anhydrides¹⁻², a solid mixture consisting of at least two components was obtained. The major component (A) could be separated from this mixture on account of its solubility in boiling petroleum ether (60°-80°) from which, on cooling it separated in shining thin plates melting at 52°-54°. A second crystallisation raised the m.p. to 55° which remained unchanged on further crystallisation.

From the petroleum ether insoluble residue a minor component (B) could be isolated by extraction with benzene and further repeated crystallisations from the same solvent till the melting point became constant at 148°. From 21 g. of the total reaction

mixture 11 g. of (A) and 2.5 g. of (B) were obtained. Their analytical data are in agreement with the compositions $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ and $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$ respectively. Both are lactone carboxylic acids and form well defined anilides and phenyl hydrazides.

That the major component (A) is one individual was established by (i) its t.l.c., (ii) analytical data of its anilide in agreement with the required composition, (iii) formation of the characteristic mono potassium salt as in the case of acids (II) with potassium content in agreement with the composition $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{K}$.

The composition $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ for (A) suggests that in its formation one of the two methylene groups of (I) is acetylated and the other butyrylated by the reagent producing (IV). The latter then cyclises to give the lactone carboxylic acid (V) which can be either (V)a or (V)b.

- a $\text{R} = \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$, $\text{R}' = \text{CH}_3$
 b $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}' = \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$

That (A) is (V)a is proved as follows. On decarboxylation by an established procedure¹⁻² (A) gave a liquid lactone (VI) $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$, b.p. 200°/55 mm. which is different from the solid lactone, m.p. 55° which we have prepared and have shown to be (VI)b. The liquid lactone must therefore be (VI)a and (A) must be (V)a.

The positive proof that (A) is (V)a is the following. Deacylation of the liquid lactone by another established procedure⁵ gave a solid lactone $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ (VI) ($\text{R}'-\text{CO} = \text{H}$) m.p. 85° which proved to be identical with the deacylation product of dehydro butyryl

acetic acid (VI) ($R = R' = C_3H_7$) previously described by one of us². The structure of (A) as (V) is thus fully established.

The structural relationship of (A) and of the above mentioned products is the following.

As in the case of dehydracetic acid (VI) ($R = R' = CH_3$) the liquid lactone (VI)a could be characterized by formation of its imido derivative (VII) m.p. 122° by warming with ammonia and of a blue crystalline copper salt of its enol. Also on boiling with hydrochloric acid the lactone ring opened followed by decarboxylation and formation of the hydrochloride of 2-*n*-propyl 6-methyl γ -pyrone (VIII) as expected. The pyrone structure of the product—a liquid b.p. 136°/2 mm—followed from the fact that a well defined crystalline hydrochloride, a chloroplatinate and a picrate could be prepared. Also on heating with ammonia in a sealed tube the crystalline pyridone (IX) was obtained.

We have described in this journal the reaction of hydrochloric acid with the isomeric lactone

(VI)b resulting in the formation of the hydrochloride of 2-methyl 6-*n*-propyl γ -pyrone (X) from which on heating with ammonia the pyridone (XI) was obtained.

Since the γ pyrone ring is flat on account of the two double bonds in it which are also symmetrically placed, and since the positions 3 and 5 are unsubstituted, the positions 2 and 6 are of equal value and therefore the substituents in these positions are interchangeable. The pyrones (VIII) and (X) are therefore expected to be identical. How far this expectation is realised could be judged from the properties of these pyrones and of their respective derivatives showed in Table I.

The I.R. absorptions of the two pyrones are almost identical.

The minor component (B): Although the composition $C_9H_{12}O_8$ of (B) is also that of dehydracetocarboxylic acid (V) ($R = R' = CH_3$) which is likely to be formed, the two acids are not identical as there is a difference in their melting points and those of their corresponding derivatives.

the acids	amides	phenyl hydrazides
(B). m.p. 148°	165°	243°
Dehydracetocarboxylic acid m.p. 154°	185°	190°

Decarboxylation of (B) by established method^{1,2} gave a product which after two crystallisations melted at 108° and was identified as dehydracetic acid (VI) ($R = R' = CH_3$). This was confirmed through formation of imido derivative m.p. 202° and formation of triacetic acid lactone (VI) ($R = CH_3, R'CO = H$) m.p. 187° which are derived from dehydracetic acid. It is thus seen that although (B) itself is not dehydraceto carboxylic acid, in the process of decarboxylation dehydracetic acid is formed. The structure of (B) is under study.

We are unable at this stage to suggest a possible mechanism of unsymmetrical acylation at two symmetrical positions of (I) by one and the same acylating agent leading to the formation of (A). But the following observations we have made are relevant to this point.

TABLE I—SHOWING PROPERTIES OF PYRONES(VIII) AND (X) AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

the pyrones	hydrochlorides	chloro Platينات	picrates	pyridones
(VIII) $C_9H_{12}O_8$ b.p. 136°/2 m.m. sparingly soluble in H_2O does not freeze.	$3(C_9H_{12}O_8)_2HCl$ m.p. 35° sparingly soluble in H_2O stem volatile.	$(C_9H_{12}O_8)_2$ $H_2Pt Cl_6$ m.p. 176°	$C_9H_{12}O_8$, $H_2(NO_2)_3 OH$ m.p. 48°	(IX) $C_9H_{12}ON$, H_2O m.p. 53°
(X) $C_9H_{12}O_8$ b.p. 128°/2 m.m. m.p. 12° soluble in H_2O	$C_9H_{12}O_8$, HCl m.p. 33° very soluble in H_2O	$(C_9H_{12}O_8)_2$ $H_2Pt Cl_6$ m.p. 175°	$C_9H_{12}O_8$, $C_6H_5(NO_2)_3 OH$ m.p. 48°	(XI) $C_9H_{12}ON$, H_2O m.p. 63°

1. (A) is formed also when (I) is acted upon by (i) a mixture of acetic and butyric anhydrides in molecular proportion, (ii) a mixture of acetic anhydride and butyric acid. The yield of (A) is however quite low in these cases.

2. A mixture of acetic and propionic anhydrides acting upon (I) fails to produce unsymmetrical acylation. Two products are formed, each of symmetrical acylation, and identified as dehydraceto carboxylic acid (V) ($R = R' = CH_3$) and dehydropropionylaceto carboxylic acid m.p. 114° (V) ($R = R' = C_2H_5$).

We are also unable to suggest a possible cause of the lack of complete identity of the pyrones (VIII) and (X).

Experimental

Acetomedicarboxylic Acid (I): This was prepared by the action of fuming sulphuric acid on citric acid as described by Ingold and Nickolls⁶.

Acetic Butyric Anhydride: This was prepared by refluxing a mixture of acetic anhydride and *n*-butyric acid and collecting the fraction at 155° – 175° as described by Autenrieth⁴.

To the anhydride (90 g.) in a 250 ml r.b. flask kept at 5° was added in instalments crude acetonedicarboxylic acid (22 g.). The temperature was maintained at 5° or below. After standing for a few minutes the mixture was gently warmed and finally heated over boiling water bath for 40 min. On cooling the contents were poured over crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered, washed and dried. Yield 28 g., m.p. of the mixture 70° – 76° .

Isolation of the components (A) and (B) :

The mixture was stirred with boiling petroleum ether (60° – 80°) and quickly filtered. Shining crystals with faint blue fluorescence of the major component (A) (V)a, slowly separated from the filtrate on cooling, with a melting point 52° – 54° which after two crystallisations become constant at 55° . Found: C, 55.2; H = 4.8. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 55.0; H = 5.0%.

The lactone carboxylic acid (V)a (2-*n*-propyl 5-acetyl 4 : 6 diketo 5 : 6 dihydro γ -pyran carboxylic acid-3) is sparingly soluble in water. It can be crystallised from benzene or dilute acetic acid.

From the petroleum ether insoluble residue the minor component (B) was extracted by hot benzene in crude form. After three crystallisations from the same solvent it melted steadily at 148° . Found: C, 50.7; H, 3.7. $C_9H_8O_6$ requires C, 50.9; H, 3.7%.

It is insoluble in petroleum ether and fairly soluble in water.

Reactions of the Lactone Carboxylic Acid (V)a :

The anilide was prepared like the anilide of dehydraceto carboxylic acid¹. Crystallised from benzene it melts at 130° . Found: N, 4.3. $C_{17}H_{17}O_5N$ requires N, 4.4%.

The monopotassium salt separated in soft feathery needles when the acid was dissolved in 10% caustic potash in excess and the solution acidified with glacial acetic acid^{1,2}. It was crystallised from 90% alcohol. Found: K, 13.8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6K$ requires K, 14.0%.

The Lactones (VI)a :

Decarboxylation of the lactone carboxylic acid (V)a by refluxing the aqueous solution of the above described mono potassium salt and then acidifying with dilute acetic acid^{1,2} gave the liquid lactone (VI)a as an oil which after washing and drying distilled at 200° – $202^\circ/55$ mm. Found: C, 61.1, H, 5.2. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 61.2; H, 6.1%.

It is a golden yellow liquid which freezes at -5° . On warming with liquor ammonia, cooling and rubbing it gave the imido derivative (VII) which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 122° . Found: N, 7.2. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 7.18%.

On neutralising (VI)a with cold caustic soda and adding cold neutral copper acetate and rubbing the copper salt of the enol separated as a blue crystalline solid. This was crystallised from aqueous alcohol. Found: Cu, 13.8. $(C_{10}H_{11}O_4)_2Cu$ requires Cu, 13.9%.

On heating with 90% sulphuric acid at 130° for a few minutes the liquid lactone was deacylated. On cooling and pouring over crushed ice the solid lactone (VI)a ($R'CO = H$) separated. It crystallised from boiling water in long colourless needles melting at 85° . Found: C, 62.1; H, 6.6. $C_8H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 62.3, H, 6.8%.

The Pyrone (VIII) :

To 15 ml of the liquid lactone (VI)a in a 250 ml r.b. flask provided with a reflux condenser, hydrochloric acid (120 ml, sp. gr. 1.16) was added. The lactone floated over the acid. On refluxing gently over a small flame the oil gradually disappeared and the liquid became turbid. After refluxing for 6 hrs and cooling a small amount of a heavy oil settled down. This was separated and the hydrochloric acid layer was distilled under reduced pressure to remove excess of the acid. The distillation was continued till about 30 ml of liquid was left. This was the main source of the pyrone hydrochloride.

From the turbid distillate a small amount of a white crystalline solid separated on cooling in an ice chest. After filtering and thoroughly draining over a porous plate previously cooled to 0° , the crystals melted at 35° and were identified as those of the pyrone hydrochloride prepared from pure pyrone and hydrochloric acid. The small amount of heavy oil referred to above also froze to crystalline solid melting at 35° and this too proved to be the pyrone hydrochloride.

The main source of the pyrone hydrochloride was the 30 ml of the liquid residue left in the flask. On adding cold caustic soda in slight excess the liberated pyrone was extracted with ether, the extract washed, dried, and the solvent removed. The residual liquid pyrone distilled at $136^\circ/2$ mm. Found: C, 71.1; H, 8.0. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71.0; H, 7.9%.

The pyrone (VIII) is a thin pale yellow liquid less soluble in water than pyrone (X). It does not freeze even when cooled to -10° .

The hydrochloride of the pyrone was prepared by adding strong hydrochloric acid (4 ml.) to the liquid pyrone (1 ml) and allowing the turbid mixture to remain in an ice chest for a few minutes. The hydrochloride separated in thin shining plates, which were quickly filtered, washed with little ice-water and dried over porous plate previously cooled to 0° in ice chest. It melts at 35° . Found: HCl, 13.4. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, HCl requires HCl, 19.3% $3(C_9H_{12}O_2)$, 2HCl requires HCl, 13.7%.

The chloroplatinate prepared by the usual method melted at 175° . Found: Pt, 27.2; $(C_9H_{12}O_2)_2 H_2Pt Cl_6$ requires Pt, 27.8%.

The picrate prepared from the pyrone, picric acid and a drop of hydrochloric acid came out as yellow needles after standing in ice chest for four days. After filtering, washing and drying it melted at 48° . Found: picric acid, 60.8. $C_9H_{12}O_2$, $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$ requires picric acid, 60.1%.

The I.R. absorptions of pyrones (VIII) and (X) important peaks are as below.

Found: C, 63.0; H, 8.7; N, 8.6. $C_9H_{13}ON$, H_2O requires C, 63.9; H, 8.8; N, 8.3%.

Reactions of the minor component (B), the acid m.p. 148° .

The phenylhydrazide was prepared by heating on waterbath a mixture of phenyl hydrazine and the acid to which was added a small amount of glacial acetic acid. The phenyl hydrazide after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 243° . Found: N, 9.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_2$ requires N, 9.3%.

The mono potassium salt was prepared as in the case of the lactone acid (V)a and was crystallised from alcohol. Found: K, 16.3. $C_9H_7O_6K$ requires K, 15.6%.

The decarboxylation of the acid through the above potassium salt was carried out as in the case of the acid (V)a. After two crystallisations of the decarboxylation product from dilute alcohol it melted at 107° and was identified as dehydracetic acid.

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INFRA RED ABSORPTIONS

Pyrone (VIII)

Wave lengths in microns	3.38	3.49	6.02	6.15	6.86	7.01	7.18	8.69	10.81	11.62
Wave numbers cm^{-1}	2950	2860	1660	1625	1457	1425	1392	1150	925	860
	M	M	V.S.	S	M	M	V.S.	M	S	M

Pyrone (X)

Wave lengths in microns	3.38	3.49	6.02	6.15	6.94	7.14	7.40	8.89	10.81	11.62
Wave numbers cm^{-1}	2950	2860	1660	1625	1440	1400	1350	1150	925	860
	W	M	V.S.	S	M	V.S.	M	M	S	M

The Pyridone (IX) was prepared by heating a mixture of pyrone (VIII) 1 ml and liquor ammonia 4 ml in a sealed tube at 130° for 4 hrs, and evaporating the contents on water bath. The thick residue on standing in ice chest for four days solidified to a thick cake. The pyridone dissolved in cold water slowly crystallised out in needles melting at 53° .

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